

Experimental Investigation of Mechanical Fiber Bundle Spreading

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Introduction

Fiber bundles are commonly used in the production of fiber-reinforced composites to achieve high mechanical performance at low weight. For efficient processing – especially during impregnation or placement – precise control of fiber guidance, spreading, and tension is essential.

However, varying fiber properties, complex interactions between tension, path, and cross-section, as well as the need for reproducibility, pose significant challenges.

A modular test rig provides a controlled environment to systematically investigate these factors and gain valuable insights for process optimization.

Test Rig

Basic setup:

- Two motor-driven axes (unwinding and winding) for continuous fiber movement
- Fully modular test section between the axes
- Integration of various measurement and process modules possible

Available components:

- Linear axis
- Light section sensors (LSS)
- Tension sensor
- Rotary encoder
- Infrared heater

Example Applications:

- Winding experiments on spherical geometries
- Quality assessment of thermoplastic impregnated tapes [1]
- Binder application on fiber bundles:
 - Application methods of binder powder
 - Melting binder using infrared heating

Roving Test Rig

Fiber Bundle Spreading

Efficient impregnation is crucial to obtain high-performance fiber-reinforced composites. It directly impacts the mechanical properties of the final part.

- Mechanical spreading of fiber bundles:
 - Increases surface area
 - Reduces matrix flow paths
 - Leads to better wetting and fewer voids
- Test rig was adjusted to investigate spreading behavior
- Fiber bundles are mechanically spread over rods
- Width and height of fiber bundle measured using light section sensors (LSS)
- Wilson's model [2] is used to predict the expected fiber bundle width ω

Presentation of Results Evaluation, Roving Width (left), Roving Width Frequency (right)

Outlook

The modular test rig enables controlled investigation of fiber bundle spreading and its impact on impregnation quality. Future work will focus on sustainable fiber materials and their specific processing challenges:

- the processing properties of staple fibers, including plant-based and recycled fibers
- the behavior of natural fibers under changing moisture conditions (e.g., water absorption, swelling, shrinkage)
- suitable strategies for quality stabilization in hygroscopic fiber systems

References

- [1] S. Neunkirchen, E. Fauster, S. Lehner, and P. O'Leary, "Instrumentation of an Inspection Test Rig for Geometry Measurement of Fiber Bundles in Automated Composite Manufacturing," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, no. 71, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2021.3132337
- [2] Wilson, S, "Lateral spreading of fibre tows", *Journal of Engineering Mathematics*, no. 32, 19-26, 1997, doi: 10.1023/a:1004253531061

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